

Community: who are we?

What does (software) sustainability mean to you?

13 Responses

Cost savings

Maintainable

Keeping software well-maintained

Creating something that can be maintained relatively straightforwardly by somebody else in the future.

Creating software that will keep working with minimal modifications from future developers/users

efficient, maintainable, understandable, adaptable to change

Reproducibility

Maintainers

Composable

What does (software) sustainability mean to you?

13 Responses

Re-usable, extensible

Useful software has a life beyond the developer who created it

reusable, modular, easy to collaborate

Software that is maintainable, with clear code, tests and documentation and reusable by other researchers.

What are potential benefits of a dashboard that displays sustainability metrics?

What are useful (sustainability) metrics currently displayed in our dashboard?

What are important metrics for you to decide/evaluate what tools to use? (And do you look at sustainability metrics?)

22 Responses

Is it being regularly updated

Regularly updated

When was it last updated?

Docs and unit tests

Number of forks, date of last update, whether CI status is passing, if there's a half-decent readme

Development Activity, Documentation

CI status

Well designed API that is well documented

version number; last release, number of contributors, docs (no particular order)

What are important metrics for you to decide/evaluate what tools to use? (And do you look at sustainability metrics?)

22 Responses

How many stars/forks

Good documentation

last update

Are developers responsive to issues and discussions?

documentation

Docs, test coverage, Issue resolve time, repo activity

Level of testing

Docs, tests, modularity

number of downloads

What are important metrics for you to decide/evaluate what tools to use? (And do you look at sustainability metrics?)

22 Responses

Response to issues

Docs (including README!), tests, CI status

I choose based on suitability to the project from a research output perspective; I judge competing tools by stars/reviews, I do not evaluate sustainability myself

For an overview of projects in team meetings

Given the example of a dashboard, how would using one add value to your work?

11 Responses

Project management - both at personal and team level.

it would motivate better code quality

To get a sense of the quality of codebases I develop.

New tool discovery

Monitor code quality

Showcase an organisation's commitment to high quality research software

Seeing multiple factors in the same place at the same time

Gives an indication of opportunities for collaboration

For an overview of projects during team meetings

Given the example of a dashboard, how would using one add value to your work?

11 Responses

Visibility of dependencies and their status

Our own libraries, improve on the matrix it reports on (add more docs, tests, ...)

What metrics and stylistic choices aren't helpful?

2 Responses

Number of lines of code is a proxy for software complexity, which is useful for many reasons, but not sure the contribution to sustainability - unless linked/weighted by other metrics, like docs etc

overall number of code lines; complex work requires more lines; readable code is more important than fewer lines but not readable.